

TWIN

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Twinning to build
an industrial
ecosystem

around the core
principles of
Industry 4.0 and
Digital Twins

X
@Twin4TwinEU

LinkedIn
Twin4Twin EU Project

Website
www.twin4twin.eu

TWIN

Digital Twin technologies
knowledge sharing

R&I Management
Upskilling

Business Development and
Networking

Demonstration of a real
digital twin use case in
advanced manufacturing